

Supplemental Data 1
(Holotype of *Climactichnites blackberriensis* Gass and Noffke, 2026)
for
New ichnotaxa from the tidal flat facies of the Cambrian Elk Mound Group,
Wisconsin, USA

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Position A (posterior extremity) to position B.

Position B to position C.

Position C to position D.

Position D to position E.

Position E to position F.

Position F to position G.

Position G to position H (anterior extremity).